

EFFECT OF GEOMETRIC ERRORS ON THE BEHAVIOUR OF MULTI-BOLT COMPOSITE JOINTS

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1 Introduction

The increased using of composite materials in aeronautical field leads to metal-composite joints which need a lot of fasteners (bolts, rivets, thread insert or bushings). The choice of joints dimensions is well understood now, thanks to many studies about their behaviour [1][2]. But the effect of geometric errors on the assembly mechanical performance is less mastered. In order to ensure mechanical performance, fastener holes are made in a single drilling operation to reduce the location error. This contributes in the increase of complete joint manufacturing time and costs.

On the one hand, complexity of damaging mechanisms implies a non-linear behaviour of composite material which complicates the modelling of the effects of geometric errors. On the other hand, experimental studies need a good control of the introduced default, and also specific instruments for the analysis of the influence of the default. Few studies dealing with the relation between geometrical variability and mechanical behaviour variability of joined structures were published. Only some studies lead by Lawlor and McCarthy deal with the effect of clearance on bolted joints behaviour in different configurations, and propose numerical and analytical models which allow estimating the implied load transfers [3]–[6].

The present study focuses on the influence of holes location error, coupled with the influence of bolt-hole clearance, on two-bolt aluminum-composite double-lap joints. The default is introduced between the holes of the composite adherent, so that once the first bolt is assembled, holes of the second bolt in composite and aluminum adherents are not aligned. A 1-D analytical model is presented, able to evaluate the preload state implied by the location error, and also to predict the load distribution between bolts when an external load is applied to the joint. The loss of stiffness, implied by bearing, is integrated in the whole bolt behaviour law, allowing the description of joint's behaviour up to fracture. This

model is validated by a 3-D finite element model (FEM) realised with Abaqus software, and also by multi-instrumented tests. The response obtained for different clearance and location error levels allows concluding about the choice of a design tolerance.

2 Analytical model description

2.1 Model formulation

The present study focuses on a two-bolt metal-composite double-lap joint, as illustrated in Fig. 1. The assembly, with a width w , is made of a composite plate, with a thickness h_1 and called substrate 1, and two aluminum plates, with a thickness h_2 and called substrate 2. The location error δp is introduced on the composite substrate, so that the composite and aluminum holes are not aligned any more. The external load F applied on the joint is divided in the two bolts. The friction loads between substrates are neglected since in composite joints the bolt tightening is quite low. The analytical model aims at evaluate the load transmitted by each fastener.

The model is based on the 1-D model proposed by Paroissien and al. [7]–[8], representing a multi-bolt joint. For n bolts, each substrate is divided in $n+1$ sections, and each section is considered as a spring, as presented in the Fig. 2. Also each bolt is considered as a spring, located in $x = d_i$.

As the assembly involves a symmetry plan, only half of the set is modeled. The load F_i , transmitted by the bolt $\#i$, is defined as:

$$F_i = k_i \left(\delta p_i + u_i^{(1)}(d_i) - u_i^{(2)}(d_i) \right) \quad (1)$$

where k_i is the stiffness of the bolt $\#i$, $u_i^{(1)}(d_i)$ and $u_i^{(2)}(d_i)$ are displacements of sections $\#i$ of both substrates, and δp_i the location error associated to the bolt $\#i$. The analytical model is illustrated in

Fig. 3. In each section # i of substrate 1, mechanical equilibrium gives:

$$\frac{dN_i^{(1)}(x)}{dx} = 0, \text{ with } i \in [1, n+1], \quad (2)$$

where $N_i^{(1)}(x)$ is half of the tension load in the substrate 1 and in section # i . The joint equilibrium gives the following equation:

$$N_i^{(1)}(x) + N_i^{(2)}(x) = \frac{F}{2}, \text{ avec } i \in [1, n+1], \quad (3)$$

where $N_i^{(2)}(x)$ is the tensile load in substrate 2. This is completed by the substrates equilibrium equation, in $x = d_i$, given by:

$$N_{i+1}^{(1)} - N_i^{(1)} = \frac{F_i}{2}, \text{ avec } i \in [1, n] \quad (4)$$

Since substrates sections are considered as linear springs, it can be written:

$$E_1 S_1 \frac{du_i^{(1)}}{dx} = N_i^{(1)}, \text{ avec } S_1 = wh_1/2 \quad (5)$$

where E_1 is the Young's modulus of substrate 1. Displacement function of first substrate's section i versus x is obtained by integrating (5):

$$u_i^{(1)}(x) = \frac{N_i^{(1)}}{E_1 S_1} (x - d_i) + u_i^{0(1)} \quad (6)$$

where $u_i^{0(1)}$ is a constant. In the same way, displacements in the second substrate are defined as:

$$u_i^{(2)}(x) = \frac{F - N_i^{(1)}}{2E_2 S_2} (x - d_i) + u_i^{0(2)} \quad (7)$$

where $S_2 = wh_2$, E_2 is the Young's modulus of the second substrate, and $i \in [1, n+1]$. The displacements continuity gives:

$$u_{i+1}^{(1)}(d_i) = u_i^{(1)}(d_i), \text{ with } i \in [1, n] \quad (8)$$

Reporting (8) in (6), one gets:

$$u_i^{0(1)} - u_{i+1}^{0(1)} + \frac{N_{i+1}^{(1)}}{E_1 S_1} (d_{i+1} - d_i) = 0, \text{ with } i \in [1, n] \quad (9)$$

Combination of equations (4) and (1) gives:

$$N_{i+1}^{(1)} - N_i^{(1)} = \frac{k_i}{2} (\delta p_i + u_i^{0(1)} - u_i^{0(2)}), \quad (10)$$

with $i \in [1, n]$. Just as the equation (9) was obtained, equations (7) and (8) give:

$$u_i^{0(2)} - u_{i+1}^{0(2)} + \frac{F - N_{i+1}^{(1)}}{2E_2 S_2} (d_{i+1} - d_i) = 0 \quad (11)$$

with $i \in [2, n+1]$. Boundary conditions are the following:

$$u_1^{0(2)} = 0 \quad (12)$$

$$N_1^{(1)} = 0 \quad (13)$$

$$N_{n+1}^{(1)} = \frac{F}{2} \quad (14)$$

A system of $3(n+1)$ equations with $3(n+1)$ unknowns is thus obtained. The unknowns are loads in adherents N_i and displacements in the joint lap, $u_i^{0(1)}$ et $u_i^{0(2)}$.

2.2 Bolt behaviour identification

Complexity of phenomenon happening around the fastener and inside the fastener during load transfer makes effective stiffness evaluation difficult (Fig. 4). Many analytical formulations were proposed, trying to get closer to the effective stiffness of a bolt joint [9]–[10], but none of them seems to be able to approach the experimental values. Furthermore they do not take into account stiffness evolutions implied by material degradation (plasticity, damaging). Bois and al. [11] proposed to model the bolt behaviour by a bilinear law, representative of bearing degradations in the composite material, as shown in Fig. 5. This law is identified both by a finite element model and tests on mono-bolt joints. The first slope is equal to k_0 , and the second one presents a stiffness equal to αk_0 , where α is a coefficient of loss of stiffness, representing bearing degradations. The clearance is also integrated in the bolt behaviour by shifting the behaviour law from the sum of the radial clearances C associated to each adherent. The analytical model

solving method consists in increasing progressively the location error value and in a second step the external load. At every increment, the secant stiffness k_i of each bolt $\#i$ is evaluated by an iterative process.

3 Validation of analytical model by finite element simulations

The present finite element model (FEM) is a 3-D model able to estimate the load transmitted by each bolt, and also stresses and displacements in composite and aluminum adherents. The assembly includes a symmetry plan, so only half of the joint is represented. The composite adherent was described as a stack of plies, with different orientations and an elastic behaviour. The aluminum adherent and the bolts were described with an isotropic elastic behaviour. Thus the FEM does not take in account material degradations. All the parameters used in the model are presented in Tab. 1.

The clearance C introduced for each bolt was taken as 0.025mm, and the location error δp as 0.150mm. Three calculation steps are necessary for solving the problem: in the first step, a small interference is introduced between the bolt head and the aluminum adherent, in order to model a low level of tightening. In the second step, the second interference generated by the location error between the second bolt body and the composite part is solved. From those two first steps, the preload state can be deduced. Finally in the third step, the external tensile load is applied to the assembly.

The evolution of the load transmitted by each fastener is plotted on Fig. 6 for both the analytical model and the FEM. Several stages can be identified along the curves obtained with the analytical model. The preload consists in generating two opposite loads on bolts. During the first stage of load application (1), the second bolt, which is in compression, is unloaded while the first bolt, which is in tension, is loaded more. When the second bolt is totally unloaded, the clearance recovery stage (2) starts. During this stage, the first bolt transfers the whole applied load. Once the clearance recovered, the second bolt is in contact with adherent holes again, and each bolt can be progressively loaded simultaneously (3). The first bolt first reaches the bearing stress, which implies a load transfer rate decrease (4). Consequently the load is reported on the second bolt, until it reaches the bearing stress (5). Furthermore, Fig. 6 makes it possible to conclude that the analytical model is able to replace

a complex finite element model for load transfer estimation in a multi-bolt joint with clearance and location error. The FEM, which contains 70 000 degrees of freedom, need about 12 hours of calculation time, whereas the analytical model only takes a few seconds.

4 Experimental validation

The tested specimen includes clearance equal to 0.025mm and location error equal to 0.150mm. Over a first step, only the first bolt is set. During the test, tensile load is applied in order to realign the holes and insert the second bolt. Afterwards, the joint is totally unloaded. The ultimate load up to failure is then applied. As expected, the failure occurs in the net-section of bolt 2. However a bearing degradation also occurs on two bolts before failure. Two gauges are placed on one of aluminum parts: the first one between the two bolts and the second one out of the lap (Fig. 7). To complete the gauge measurement, the specimen is covered by a black and white speckle in order to measure the displacement and strain fields by digital image correlation. These field measurements allow us controlling the bending effect which can disturb the test analysis. The three first stages previously described in Fig. 6 can be seen in **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.** which compares the strains observed experimentally (gauge #1) and those obtained numerically. Indeed, the preload state and the clearance recovery stage appear clearly. Beyond the bearing initiation, the results cannot be compared, since the bearing degradation is not included in the FEM.

4. Exploitation of the analytical model

One of the potential use of the analytical model is the choice of tolerances for joint design and manufacturing in order to control the ratio cost/performance of the assembly. In the example illustrated in Fig. 9 and Fig. 10, an acceptable permanent hole deformation, called c_0 is first defined according to design rules coming, for example, from fatigue strength requirements. This value gives the maximal load F_{c_0} which can be transmitted by each bolt. It means that the maximal acceptable external load F_{max} is achieved when one of the bolt loads reaches F_{c_0} .

Fig. 9 presents the influence of the location error on the ratio between F_{max} and the theoretical maximal load given by $2F_{c_0}$. This ratio is representative of the joint performance. Let us say that a loss of

performance λ equal to 10% can be acceptable. Thanks to the analytical model, the maximal location error can easily be obtained and used to choice and define the flow process grid.

5 Conclusions

In this study, an analytical model which is able to represent load transfer in a multi-bolt double-lap joint is proposed. It is validated by a numerical model and experimental results allow confirming the interest of the analytical model. The study of 2-D assemblies and single-lap configuration will be the next challenge of this work.

Double lap joint dimensions	Composite thickness h_1 (mm) 4 (16 plies)	Aluminum thickness h_2 (mm) 5	Overlap length L (mm) 80	Pas p (mm) 40	Bolt diameter d (mm) 6.35	
Properties of the unidirectional ply for T700/M21 used in FEM	E_{11} (GPa) 130.3	$E_{22} = E_{33}$ (GPa) 7.6	$G_{12} = G_{13}$ (GPa) 4.75	G_{23} (GPa) 2.65	$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$ 0.33	ν_{23} 0.43
Homogenised properties for T700/M21 quasi-isotropic lay-up used in analytical model	E_{xx} (GPa) 48	Laminate ultimate stress σ_u (MPa) 600	Bearing pressure p_{b1} (MPa) 433			
Properties for Aluminium alloy 6061 used in FEM and analytical model	E (GPa) 68	ν 0.3				
Titanium (Hi-Lock Bolt) properties used in FEM	E (GPa) 106	ν 0.3	Yield stress σ_e (MPa) 830			
Bolt joint properties used in analytical model	Stiffness k_0 (kN/mm) 127	Relative stiffness reduction α 0.151				

Tab. 1. Material and geometrical parameters used in the analytical model and in the FEM

Fig. 1. Dimensions of double-lap metal-composite joint with locating default

Fig. 2. Principle scheme of the analytical model

Fig. 3. Description of the 1-D model of a metal-composite multi-bolt assembly

Fig. 4. Illustration of mechanical phenomena involved in the relative displacement of adherents.

Fig. 5. Load versus experimental displacement for a double-lap joint with $d/w = 0.21$, bolt clamping of 1.3 Nm and a bolt-hole diametric clearance of 0.02 mm.

Fig. 6. Loads F_1 and F_2 transmitted by the bolts versus load for $C = 0.025$ mm and $\delta p = 0.150$ mm

Fig. 7. a) Description of an aluminum-composite double-lap specimen before test. b) Description of the test device.

Fig. 8. Comparison of strains obtained with the gauge #1 and those obtained with the FEM

Fig. 9. Definition of the acceptable permanent hole deformation c_0

Fig. 10. Evolution of the maximal acceptable external load according to the location error.

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